

Theoretical foundations and reflections on the need to systematize a common lexicon in English for the behavioral sciences

Fundamentos teóricos y reflexiones sobre la necesidad de sistematizar un léxico común en Inglés para las ciencias del comportamiento

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ABSTRACT

More and more, mental health has been a topic of high concern and relevance. Emotions, behaviors and well-being are aborded with a deeper view and interest by society since the need to understand some patterns of behavior in human beings are the answer to deal with many social, academic, professional, even economic concerns. However, people still don't apply the psychological terms correctly. Hence, they present a special focus to avoid confusion and to facilitate people to use them accurately. Therefore, this article is

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aimed at presenting a theoretical and reflective foundation that justify the need to systematize a common lexicon in Psychology as a referential point for clarification of essential psychological terms in accessible language to students, teachers, professionals, and people in general; to bridge the gap between academic discourse and everyday communication on mental health. This manuscript provides a rich approach to several sub areas of psychology, such as basic, educational, social, cognitive, organizational, clinical, forensic, health, neuroscientific, environmental, community, and art psychology. The methodology is documentary, with a qualitative design through the collection and analysis of 2019 -2025 scholarly sources, that support the importance of the systematization of a shared lexicon. As a result, this article proves that language and terminology are essential to shape the development of psychological knowledge and communication by reflecting and discussing the theoretical foundation for a systematization of a common vocabulary and terminology in Psychology. In addition, this study is an open resource for the creation of Psychology glossaries and updates in future studies to improve the interdisciplinary communication, research replicability, and teaching-learning paths across psychology subfields.

Keywords: *english for specific purposes, psychology, theoretical foundation, mental health, lexicon systematization*

RESUMEN

Cada vez más, la salud mental se ha transformado en un tema de gran preocupación y relevancia. Las emociones, el comportamiento y el bienestar son abordados con una perspectiva e interés más profundo por la sociedad, dada la necesidad de entender más al ser humano como respuesta para lidiar con problemas de índole social, académica, profesional, e inclusive económica. Sin embargo, las personas aún no usan apropiadamente los términos psicológicos. Por consiguiente, abordarlos presentan un enfoque especial para evitar confusión y para facilitar el uso acertado de ellos. Por lo tanto, este artículo tiene como fin presentar fundamentos teóricos y reflexivos que justifican la necesidad de sistematizar un léxico común en psicología para aclarar términos psicológicos esenciales en un lenguaje exequible para los estudiantes, docentes, profesionales y demás interesados, con el fin de cerrar las brechas entre el discurso académico y la comunicación cotidiana en torno a la salud

mental. Este manuscrito ofrece un rico enfoque a diversas sub áreas de psicología, como la básica, educativa, social, cognitiva, organizacional, clínica, forense, de salud, neurociencia, ambiental, con enfoque en la comunidad y al arte. La metodología del estudio es documental, con un diseño cualitativo, a través de la colección y análisis de recursos académicos del 2019 al 2025, con un total de 125 ítems estudiados, que consolidan la importancia de la sistematización de un léxico común. Como resultado, este estudio prueba que tanto la lengua como la terminología son esenciales para formar el desarrollo del conocimiento psicológico y la comunicación, a través de la reflexión y discusión de fundamentos teóricos para la sistematización de un vocabulario común en psicología. Además, este estudio está abierto para tomarse como base a la creación de un glosario psicológico y a actualizaciones en futuros estudios para mejorar la comunicación interdisciplinaria, la replicabilidad y el proceso de enseñanza-aprendizaje entre sub áreas de psicología.

***Palabras claves:** inglés para propósitos específicos, psicología, fundamento teórico, salud mental, sistematización del léxico*

INTRODUCCIÓN

Psychology has come a long way from its philosophical origins to become the science that we know today. It is increasingly common for people to talk about mental health, emotions, and well-being, which has generated a greater need to better understand human behavior. However, with this popularization, confusion has also arisen, especially when psychological terms are used without knowing their true meaning. Therefore, it is essential to possess tools that facilitate a comprehensive understanding of this domain and are readily accessible.

Since ancient times, humans have tried to understand the factors that affect each person's thoughts, feelings, and actions. Philosophers like Aristóteles and Plato have pondered the nature of humanity, the spirit, and the alma, expressing interest in how these things arise and function in the outside world. The current scientific research indicates that these changes are closely related to the brain, environment, and past experiences (Ardila, 2022).

In this context, the idea of developing an article as a foundation to create a systematization of lexicon in Psychology was born for psychology technicians. The general objective of this research is to justify the need of a tool that serves as a reference for students, teachers, professionals, and even people who are simply curious about this discipline. Often, a misunderstood word can completely change the meaning of a diagnosis, a class, or a conversation about mental health. Certain reliable sources make it easier to disseminate accurate and responsible information while attempting to reduce misunderstandings.

Furthermore, it is important to explain in detail the three specific objectives of this proposal: first, to analyze the theoretical bases that reinforce the need for a system that explain key psychological terms in language that is understandable and contemporary for students and professionals; second, to critically reflect on the implications of the diversity of psychological terminology in behavioral science justifying why the systematization of a common lexicon is essential. Third, to explore the pedagogical and practical implications of a system of shared terminology in English for specific purposes.

This work also seeks to be a reflective, conceptual and epistemological base for a useful tool for learning and teaching which is intended that anyone can find the meaning of key psychological terms, understand what context is used, see examples, and make connections with other concepts. It is a solid support for a resource that can serve in the classroom, in clinical work, or even in everyday life, as we hear more and more about anxiety, self-esteem, empathy, trauma, among many other concepts that are part of the common language, but they have a very specific technical background.

Furthermore, by developing this foundation, a basis for a common language is created that allows different people, students, teachers, therapists, and curious readers to talk about psychology in a more coherent and precise way. In a field as broad as this, where many branches of knowledge intersect, it is essential to agree on what certain terms mean. Thus, not only will it improve communication, but it will also promote a deeper understanding of what it really means to study the mind and behavior.

One of the biggest challenges facing psychology is that its jargon can be difficult for those unfamiliar with the field. This section aims to translate the jargon into more understandable language without sacrificing academic rigor. The primary goal is to provide a pillar for practical, accessible, and reliable resource for everyone, from first-year students to professionals with

extensive experience in the field of psychology and all its derivatives. This will bring psychological knowledge to a wider audience, especially in a society where mental health is becoming increasingly important and complex due to the different factors and behaviors that arise in each individual.

In terms of methodology, this project follows a qualitative and descriptive approach. This means that the content has been carefully indexed to provide a valid support to sustain the need of the creation of a system that organizes words in alphabetical order, along with definitions, examples, and references in both Spanish and English, not as a simple list; but to facilitate learning and practical application. The goal is to provide the basis for future studies that aim at simplifying to learners to develop a solid foundation of knowledge as they become familiar with the concepts of this science.

In short, this study aims to strengthen the lexical components as key parts of English for Psychology Science as a bridge between the academic world and everyday life, by creating a systematization (glossary) that instead of making what already seems difficult more complicated, transform it into something more accessible and more human. Because we all, at some point, need to understand how our mind or that of others works. Whether to study, teach, work with people, or simply to know ourselves better, psychological language can be a very powerful guide, as long as it is understood well.

The motivation behind this project also has a social root, due to living in a time when talking about emotions, thoughts, and behaviors is no longer taboo. But that is also involved: the responsibility of using the right words, understanding what they mean, and applying them carefully. A misinterpretation can not only led to confusion, but it could even affect important decisions, such as a diagnosis or therapeutic intervention. Therefore, this material seeks to provide clarity and confidence.

Finally, this research is aimed at a wide audience, including psychology students, university professors, clinical professionals, researchers, and anyone who is simply interested in better understanding how the human mind and behavior work. It also seeks to convey the idea that psychology is not limited to being an academic subject, but rather constitutes an essential aspect of our daily lives, promoting a clearer understanding of our environment and helping to prevent consequences with a significant impact. By supporting a systematization of psychological concepts in a more accessible way, students will be able to gain a deeper

understanding and apply them in a more relevant way in their daily lives.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

"Global mental health" has gained great relevance since it was established as a field specific from the series published by the magazine *The Lancet* in 2007. This milestone marked a before and after by positioning mental health as a priority within the global health agenda. One of the main contributions of this series was its call to action to expand the mental health services in low- and middle-income countries, as well as the creation of the Global Mental Health Movement, which unified previously scattered efforts (Misra, Stevenson, Haroz, de Menil, & Koenen, 2019).

The term global mental health was originally defined as "the improvement of mental health," and the achievement of this was equitable access to healthcare for people around the world. According to Misra et al. (2019), it has become a unifying factor for integrating mental health into global health agendas and is now widely present in academic curricula. This reflects the growing relevance of the various disciplines linked to general psychology. Given the increase in cases, an understanding based on common terminology is essential to unify criteria. In this way, precise definitions contribute to harmonizing mental health practices in work, educational, and clinical settings, among others.

The year 2007 marked a significant shift in the scientific success of mental health. The number of peer-reviewed articles using the term increased from 12 in 2007 to 114 in 2016, while the number of citations increased 16.5. This increase reflects not only growing interest but also the global emphasis on mental health as a public health priority. Institutions such as Harvard and Johns Hopkins began incorporating this term into their academic programs, strengthening its academic and political influence. This research suggests specific terms that help professionals and the general public understand basic and specific psychological terminology related to mental health.

Misra et al. (2019) identified the main priorities for global mental health research, establishing key areas based on a critical analysis. The most significant change in their research was the transition to empirical studies; while early work focused solely on theoretical approaches, evidence-based research began to predominate from 2015 onwards. This change highlights the need to address mental health from a measurable and verifiable perspective. The

focus on empirical evidence reinforces the scientific soundness of global mental health programs and, at the same time, supports decision-making that prioritizes mental health care.

Another important finding of this review is that studies focusing on mental health have been conducted in low- and middle-income countries, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia. These communities have acute mental health needs, but these are often neglected due to a lack of resources. Common issues include anxiety, mental illness, stress-related disorders, and depression. However, areas requiring greater support and attention are also highlighted.

Nevertheless, other relevant areas, such as dementia, suicide, and mental health in general, continue to receive little attention, which translates into a limited number of scientific studies. This lack of attention generates complex problems that affect a large number of people and have not yet been sufficiently addressed by scientific research. It is imperative to address this gap to meet the unique mental health requirements of distinct communities. This mismatch highlights the need to diversify research initiatives. Such an approach would more effectively address the comprehensive range of mental health challenges affecting diverse groups globally.

Finally, the authors emphasize a significant deficiency in several worldwide mental health studies: the lack of contextual information. Important factors such as the exact location of the study, the language spoken, the ethnicity of the participants, economic background, and religious beliefs are often omitted. This lack of information weakens the validity and relevance of the results and conclusions, especially across different cultures. Identifying this shortcoming highlights the need for resources such as specialized glossaries to help students, professionals, and the general public understand key ideas about mental health. Clear language promotes accountability in the practice of psychology.

Psychology is important in all aspects of human life, for example, how the COVID-19 pandemic was experienced. This global health crisis has shown that vulnerability goes beyond physical appearance; it also affects mental health, impacting people who are shy, anxious, or have low resilience. Emotional instability can have a profound effect on behavior, damaging overall health. Therefore, the close connection between the mind, cognition, and the body often manifests itself in fatigue, headaches, limited physical activity, or impaired immune function.

These findings highlight the importance of integrating mental health into public health in order to understand the direct impact of mental health on physical illness, emphasizing the

importance of an integrative approach. Therefore, mental health care, along with medical care, should be a priority in public health initiatives in order to help those with specific and clear mental and emotional health problems in the first instance. This approach guarantees a comprehensive strategy to protect communities, particularly during crises.

According to Hawke et al. (2022), in their systematic review, to promote strong mental health, good cognitive functioning, and comprehensive psychological well-being. On the other hand, mental health also encompasses dimensions such as depression, anxiety, and other disorders that require rigorous analysis for an accurate diagnosis. Cognition refers to mental processes involving memory, attention, and reasoning. Mental well-being, on the other hand, refers to the psychological state related to memory, attention, and thinking, and includes aspects such as quality of life and personal satisfaction.

Therefore, it is essential to know and understand the terminology related to mental health, as many concepts are closely related to physical illnesses, including COVID-19. Maintaining a healthy and balanced mind acts as a protective factor against various conditions and promotes faster and more effective recovery. The glossary as a systematization of common lexicon is relevant to present and define key terms to facilitate a deeper understanding and their application in academic and professional contexts.

Another study revealed the impact of COVID-19 since 2020 on the mental health of all age groups, including children, adolescents, and adults. This unexpected situation has left many people unprepared for the emotional and psychological consequences, leading to an increase in cases of depression, anxiety, stress, and other illnesses that affect mental and emotional health. In the face of this crisis, it was essential to provide support through online therapy as a form of rapid and accessible assistance.

In this context, Almeda, Díaz-Milanés, Gutiérrez-Colosía, and García-Alonso (2022) conducted a systematic review of global mental health policies and assessments to adapt them to digital platforms during the epidemic. Professionals received various interventions from individuals providing simple treatment in the first instance based on strategies and recommendations related to mental health according to the diagnosis of those with mental health problems.

Among patients with psychological problems, the most frequent topics include recommendations for promoting mental well-being, managing stress and anxiety, particularly

those related to COVID-19, strategies for reducing stigma, support for victims of domestic violence, promoting healthy lifestyles, as well as online therapy and remote psychological assessment services. These resources were particularly significant for patients and reflect the growing need for accessible and personalized mental health support, both in face-to-face and virtual clinical settings.

Thus, the implementation of online care seeks not only to reduce the negative impact of the virus on mental health, but also to prevent the spread of infection. Telepsychiatry has become an important tool for outpatient care, with increased telephone or face-to-face contact with general practitioners, who are the first point of contact for psychiatric services (Almeda et al., 2022). Online services have reduced geographical and administrative barriers, allowing more people to access care quickly.

This research concludes that online psychological support strategies have become increasingly important given the magnitude of the global impact of COVID-19 on mental health. This has helped maintain access to services during physical contact restrictions, providing structured responses to emerging patient needs and thus mitigating the onset or worsening of mental health problems during the pandemic. Online assistance has paved the way for the integration of digital tools into care systems to improve long-term mental health.

In addition, a positive association has been identified between mental health and reducing obesity rates in young people. Hoore et al. (2015), in a systematic review of mental health and well-being following community interventions aimed at obesity prevention, found a bidirectional relationship between the two conditions. In other words, obesity not only has a negative impact on mental health, but mental disorders can also affect weight. This highlights the importance of comprehensive interventions that address the physical, mental, and emotional health of young people.

Adolescence, a period of significant physical, hormonal, emotional, and social changes, represents a period of increased risk for unhealthy weight and mental health problems. The review suggests that obesity prevention strategies should take special care not to cause psychological harm, as factors such as body image and weight perception can have a significant impact on adolescents' self-esteem. Therefore, healthcare should promote overall well-being, prioritize healthy habits, and avoid reinforcing negative stereotypes.

A key finding is that reducing anxiety symptoms, along with increased self-esteem and

confidence, contributes significantly to improving mental well-being (Hoare et al., 2015). In this regard, it is essential to develop sustainable treatments that promote nutritious eating, regular physical activity, and attention to emotional aspects. Future research should systematically consider the multiple factors linked to overall well-being (physical, mental, and emotional) to ensure a truly comprehensive approach. Such an approach ensures that interventions address both the physical health and psychological needs of individuals.

Another important concept in mental health is the term “psychotic,” which refers to people with schizophrenia, a serious mental disorder that affects thinking, mood, and perception of reality. The Cambridge English Dictionary defines “psychotic” as “psychosis (serious mental illness).” A person with schizophrenia experiences a profound disconnect from reality, often characterized by hallucinations (perceptions of things that do not exist), delusions (persistent false beliefs), and other symptoms.

On the other hand, Bhavsar et al. (2018) conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis. Bhavsar et al. (2018) conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis that examined psychological experiments (PE) and their association with the use of mental health services. The objective was to determine whether individuals who reported PE were more likely to use these services and whether this association remained even when controlling for other mental health problems, such as depression, anxiety, or suicidal behavior. Their results highlight the importance of early assessment and management of patients with PE to improve mental health and reduce long-term consequences.

The preliminary results of that study suggest that it is still unclear whether psychological problems influence the use of mental health care or whether this relationship is moderated by individual psychopathologies. This distinction is important because it has a direct impact on diagnosis and clinical treatment. Understanding these trends helps to improve interventions and optimize the allocation of mental health resources. It also underscores the importance of rigorous assessments in healthcare settings.

That review revealed two important findings: (1) few studies addressed coexisting psychopathologies; and (2) when adjusting for conditions such as depression and anxiety, the association between PD and mental health service use was significantly reduced (Bhavsar et al., 2018). This highlights the need for future research to adopt a more rigorous approach that considers the complexity of multiple mental health outcomes, given that this topic

encompasses comprehensive issues.

The authors suggest that this association could be due to residual confounding factors, suggesting that a more accurate assessment of other mental disorders, along with other factors, could predict the effects of these factors. This highlights the need for comprehensive diagnostic testing to avoid overestimating the independent impact of EP.

It's fundamental to create a glossary that aims to provide accurate definitions of key topics such as mental health, physical health, isolation, substance abuse, bullying, and social deprivation, recognizing the complexity of the mind and its multiple causes and conditions. This study goal is to provide a base for the creation of essential tools for professionals, laypeople, and practitioners who wish to improve their understanding of mental health issues. Through clear definitions, it also promotes effective communication and decision-making for a fairly assertive clinical diagnosis.

Another systematic review related to the study by Tam et al. (2024), who examined the effects of television programs aimed at raising awareness about mental health among young people on different media platforms. The campaigns, which are broadcast on television, websites, and social media, have the overall goal of raising awareness, reducing stigma, and encouraging young people aged 10 to 24 to seek immediate help.

Studies show that, in general, these practices have a positive impact on young people's attitudes, beliefs, and behaviors. However, the authors emphasize the need to implement consistent and standardized criteria to improve the future of these practices. They also highlight the importance of incorporating cultural competence and active citizen participation in the design of television campaigns to ensure their relevance and effectiveness in reducing problems of anxiety, depression, or stress.

The study conducted by Diel et al. (2024) underscores a significant aspect of digital interventions aimed at assisting patients with mental health issues. These interventions, termed e-mental health (EMH), encompass approaches aimed at providing effective treatment for mental diseases through electronic methods and channels. This includes systems based on mobile applications, web platforms, text messages (SMS), videos, or digital monitoring. The term EMH covers any intervention that is delivered digitally with the aim of improving mental health outcomes.

This approach is especially designed to benefit people with complex mental disorders

who reside in rural areas, as well as to reduce long waiting times for receiving specialized care. Additionally, these tools are useful to ensure the stabilization of the patient and prevent the deterioration of their mental health status (Diel et al., 2024). In conclusion, digital interventions have proven to be effective in improving clinical outcomes. Although the study was conducted in Western Europe, it is suggested that this strategy could be viable in other parts of the world, as long as there is an internet connection that allows its implementation.

Currently, Artificial intelligence is increasingly influencing psychology, with professionals incorporating it into clinical evaluations and reports. Guo et al. (2024) highlight the importance of low-level languages (LLs) for communicating with experts and the general public. These models are fast and accurate for analyzing medical records and diagnosing diseases. However, their use presents challenges. Research involving humans is important. The law is strictly enforced.

The report concludes that mental health professionals, particularly those using artificial intelligence (LLMs), cannot and should not be replaced by mental health professionals. However, their rapid development reveals great potential as medical support devices, highlighting the need for further development of these technologies with particular attention to psychology. Their performance must be periodically evaluated by healthcare professionals to ensure compliance with ethical requirements and patient safety.

It should be emphasized that the use of large language models (LLMs) in psychiatric disorders requires experience and particular attention. These technological assistance models improve accessibility, streamline processes, and facilitate data analysis. However, patient safety and ethics must remain paramount. To this end, research must raise awareness in humans to enable accurate clinical interpretation based on diagnosis and expert criteria.

Grant's (2024) study on human development examines the factors that determine a person's cognitive and social growth. In particular, it emphasizes character skills such as initiative, discipline, and determination, not as inherent traits, but as abilities that can be acquired and developed over time. In this way, this perspective challenges traditional beliefs about talent and natural potential, providing a more robust and inclusive understanding of personal development. Finally, Grant's approach encourages active participation in personal development, regardless of initial circumstances. His views are especially beneficial for educators and mental health practitioners aiming to facilitate enduring, significant

transformation.

Moreover, the author transcends mere theoretical exposition by offering pragmatic solutions grounded in psychological facts to facilitate transformation and realize individual potential. Among these actions, he suggests asking for advice instead of opinions, practicing intentionally through “deliberate play”, teaching what you want to learn, and focusing the interviews on highlighting character skills and potential. This research is mentioned because the content of the book will serve as a basis for the development of a glossary that will provide support for students, teachers, and the general public.

In the educational field, psychology also plays a fundamental role in the teaching-learning process. The study conducted by Bello Ávila, Cedeño Santacruz, Fernández Conforme, and Carrillo Bello (2025) highlights, from the perspective of neuroscience and educational psychology, the relevance of implementing classrooms adapted to the neurological functioning of students. Furthermore, it this study highlights the need for ongoing teacher training in neuroeducation. The use of personalized interventions and continuous monitoring of learning was considered essential.

This is particularly important given the growing number of children with special educational needs. Therefore, it is crucial that teachers and school administrators actively participate in all school activities. The full participation of students with special needs is the responsibility of the training team. In this context, neuroeducation becomes essential for providing quick responses in the classroom. Its role is to support teachers' practices in dynamic educational environments.

The study also shows that neuroscience and educational sciences offer information about the brain behavior of children with disorders such as autism spectrum disorder (ASD) or attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD). All these terms are directly linked to the discipline of psychology. Understanding this allows us to tailor teaching to the specific needs of each student. In this way, more effective educational interventions can be designed based on both basic and specialized psychological theories.

Another field with the highest demand today is forensic psychology, due to the increase in cases related to child custody, domestic violence, harassment, and cases of gender violence, among others. In the book “Forensic Psychology: Study of the Criminal Mind”, Amar Amar and Torado García (2010) cited the authors cite Hess (1999), who defines this discipline as the one

responsible for providing psychological services in the judicial or legislative context, developing knowledge linked to legal aspects, whether from psychology "for the law" or "of the law".

From this perspective, the forensic psychologist can perform various functions, such as criminal profiler, child custody evaluator, counselor, therapist, police officer, prison psychologist, expert witness, or scientific researcher (Amar Amar & Torado García, 2010, p. 11). Finally, their mission is to illustrate, advise, and provide technical knowledge to the judge or court, thus becoming a key collaborator in the administration of justice. In conclusion, Forensic psychology aims to comprehend both the illegal act and the perpetrator.

Ethics in organizations and the function of the organizational psychologist have been established as essential foundations for institutional fortification in Latin America (Moncayo-Ortiz, Villota-Torres, Matabanchoy-Salazar, & Figueroa-Peña, 2023). From an organizational or industrial perspective, the role of the psychologist is particularly relevant due to the complexity of dealing with large groups of people. Moncayo-Ortiz et al. (2023) highlight that the organizational psychologist performs various functions within the organization and is key to human resource management.

One of their main tasks is to ensure the implementation of ethical standards among employees, thereby promoting good performance at the personal, professional, and cultural levels. In addition, organizational psychologists promote personal and corporate behavior. Their intervention is important in managing behavioral problems, always seeking to minimize potential harm to the employee and the organization (Moncayo-Ortiz, 2023).

Furthermore, their work contributes significantly to improving work-life, productivity, and team performance. Despite the importance of their work, the authors point out that there is little academic literature that describes in depth the work of psychologists and how important it is for companies. This highlights the need for more research examining people's behaviors in different workplaces and industries. Expanding this knowledge can help organizations develop better ways to promote employee well-being and performance.

Another important area that has become increasingly relevant in psychology today is environmental psychology. Villalpando-Flores (2022) defines this discipline as a scientific field that studies transactions between human beings and their sociophysical environments. Beyond this definition, environmental psychology analyzes how urban, socio-spatial, and social-community planning processes and psycho-environmental factors affect the perception of the

immediate environment, influence the quality of life, and sustainability (pp.2).

This approach is key to questioning, analyzing, and evaluating how contexts, socio-spatial processes, whether immediate or extended, can facilitate or limit cognitive processes, behavioral, and emotional aspects linked to the care of nature, with the ultimate goal of improving the quality of life and promoting a more sustainable lifestyle. This field studies the relationship between cities, architecture, and territory, while also addressing the creation of social spaces, recognizing that these places are closely linked to well-being and quality of life in urban contexts.

Such approaches promote more efficient planning, aimed at both responding to the needs of the population and preserving the environment. From this perspective, urban design takes on a fundamental role, as it shapes human life and has a decisive influence on the daily routine of its inhabitants. In short, environmental psychology is a fundamental discipline for understanding the complex interaction between humans and their built environment, particularly in urban contexts, with the aim of promoting habitability, well-being, and sustainability through design-conscious, inclusive, and sensitive urban design to both psychological and social needs (Villalpando-Flores, 2022).

In this context, it is worth investigating and analyzing various sources derived from psychology with the purpose of building a solid pillar to design a specialized glossary that aims at the broad field of this. This material provides a comprehensive review of the disciplines of mental health, human behavior, human development, environment, art, culture, and related disorders that directly affect the well-being of children, adolescents, young adults, and youth. The project seeks to prove the importance of explaining complex psychological concepts, improving understanding and accessibility through a glossary as a systematization of common lexicon.

This set of terms will allow us to group together key terms related to the discipline of psychology, with the aim of providing a useful and accessible resource for both teachers and students in this field. Thus, the glossary will not only function as a reference tool for immediate response to doubts, but also as a means to foster academic growth and professional development in this area of knowledge. Ultimately, it seeks to strengthen communication and deepen understanding of essential psychological concepts.

METHODOLOGY

This research uses a documentary and qualitative methodology, focused on the collection, analysis, and interpretation of data from scientific and theoretical bibliographic sources. Furthermore, this methodology facilitates the exploration, understanding, and organization of current psychological knowledge through a systematic and critical evaluation of professional literature. Likewise, the descriptive and documentary aspect of the methodology allows for a clear and structured backing of the relevance of creating a classification and presentation of concepts, terminology, and conclusions, without manipulation of variables.

The documentary population consisted of written sources, including books, indexed articles, scientific reports, academic theses, and systematic reviews, published between 2019 and 2025, covering subdisciplines such as basic psychology, developmental, clinical, educational, organizational, and social psychology. In total, 125 sources were investigated during the process, and the documentary sample was selected using relevance criteria, subject matter, current events, availability of full content, and academic relevance.

The sources were obtained from reliable databases such as Scopus, Google Scholar, Scielo, as well as from institutional repositories and digital libraries that provide documents in the PDF format. The compilation technique is based on thematic analysis, and categorization was performed by different types of psychologists, which allows concepts to be organized according to their scope. This methodological approach enabled the exhaustive and systematic compilation of relevant psychological terms.

Likewise, bibliographic cards were used as a recording instrument, where relevant data such as the identified term, its contextual definition, translation (English-Spanish), original source, and year of publication were recorded. To ensure linguistic accuracy, used the Cambridge dictionary as the primary source of verification in English and the APA Dictionary of Psychology and Thesaurus.com as a complementary source.

As a result of the analysis, frequently used terms in theses, articles, and books were identified as specialized in the field of Psychology. Based on these inputs, a foundation was established to advocate for the creation of a systematical structure that includes: Term in English, Translation into Spanish, Brief definition in English, and Example of contextual use.

The fundamental criteria are aimed to be a referential point that triggers aspects such as:

- Frequency of use in academic Psychology texts written in English.

- Relevance to the content of the degree program.
- Clarification of the term, its definition, and its use in both contexts.

Methodological justification

The choice of a documentary and qualitative methodology is justified by the nature of the objective proposed: the construction of a theoretical foundation for a technical glossary specialized in Psychology, with a focus on English for specific purposes. This research does not seek to quantify phenomena, but to analyze, classify, and systematize key concepts from reliable academic sources. Such an approach allows for a deeper understanding of terminology within specific psychological contexts and academic discourse.

Furthermore, the qualitative approach allows for a deep interpretation of the content, respecting the context in which the selected terms are used. For its part, the documentary nature responds to the need to collect accurate and up-to-date information from the existing scientific literature, which constitutes the basis for developing a rigorous and pedagogical resource contextualized. Therefore, this methodology is consistent with the purpose of offering a useful tool for learning, consultation, and professional application by students of Psychology.

RESULTS

In this section, the foundation for the creation of a solid systematization of a common lexicon in English for the behavioral sciences is constructed.

English for Specific Purposes

Across recent decades, the acquisition of the English language has evolved to meet the specific needs of many professional and academic fields, leading to the development of English for Specific Purposes (ESP). This section emphasizes the linguistic and communicative requirements of fields such as medicine, law, and psychology. Hutchinson and Waters (1987) stated that English for Specific Purposes (ESP) is based on the principle that linguistic content and teaching methods must meet the needs of students, making it an effective tool for those pursuing technical or scientific careers.

In psychology, proficiency in technical English is essential, as primary materials such as the DSM-5, ICD-11, and most scientific research are published in English. Therefore, this

language proficiency allows students and professionals to stay up to date, apply international standards, and expand their knowledge in their respective fields. The lack of this proficiency hinders their professional development and the quality of care, making English proficiency essential in contemporary psychology.

In mental health, appropriate terminology is essential for accurate diagnosis and treatment based on the interdisciplinary communication that psychology itself requires. Syaufika and Ambarwati (2023) emphasized that English proficiency is an essential skill in several disciplines, especially in psychology, where accuracy must prevail for correct diagnosis and treatment. Acquiring this competency guarantees ethical, high-quality work and enables professionals to contribute successfully in worldwide communities.

Therefore, the incorporation of ESP in the education of learners in psychology not only enhances their comprehension of foreign academic content but also strengthens their communication competencies to perform in multilingual therapeutic environments. The mastery of technical English supports the professionalization of students, expanding their professional opportunities and permitting their active participation in global scientific networks (Dudley-Evans & St John, 1998).

To address this academic need, we propose the development of a technical English glossary specifically for psychology students. This resource will be useful in various professional contexts, such as clinical, environmental, forensic, and community psychology, as well as for correct clinical application, allowing professionals and students to use technical content appropriately. Its main objective is to promote the understanding of specialized terms and strengthen language acquisition within psychology, in line with the academic offerings of the Technical University of Babahoyo.

Below are some terms that often cause confusion for the psychologist or specialist. The following table provides a clearer and more concise version of these concepts, intended to facilitate a broader analysis and allow appropriate interventions, either in the context of a clinical evaluation or in the development of a diagnosis.

Table 1.

Clarification of psychological terms between cognitive and social psychology

Auth or(s)	Ye ar	Psycho logic terms	Conce ptual Gap or Confusion	Defin ition	Applic ation or Proposed solution
Yin & Wang	(2 023)	Uncon scious	Ambig uity between conscious and unconscious processes	The unconscious directs much of human behavior	Use in psychoanalysis to interpret dreams and symptoms
Gibson	(2 024)	Cognit ive development	Confu sion about the limits of developmental stages	Learn ing occurs in phases (sensorimotor , preoperationa l, etc.)	Applic ed in education to adapt teaching methods to cognitive stages.
Halo nen, Appleby, & Brewer	(2 023)	Social Learning	Mistak en reduction to mere imitation	Learn ing occurs through observation and modeling	Applic ed in behavioral therapies and educational programs.
Halliday	(2 024)	Attach ment	Diffic ulty distinguishing secure from insecure attachment	Early bonds with caregivers affect emotional development	Applic ed in child psychology and clinical interventions.
American Psychologica l Association	(2 022).	Anxiet y Disorder	Confu sion between stress and clinical anxiety	Anxi ety: persistent worry with psychological symptoms.	Treat ed with CBT, mindfulness, or medication.

Note. Based on documentary analysis of all areas related to Psychology (2022-2024).

Table 1 describes terms from different perspectives that have been shaped by their understanding, and this has evolved due to psychological phenomena. This contains the term author, year, definition, and application.

Ying and Wang’s unconscious concept illustrates how early psychoanalytic theory emphasized hidden processes that influence behavior, while Gibson cognitive development framework focused on observable stages of childhood learning. In Halonen et al., social learning theory and attachment theory, observational processes were highlighted as important, while behavioral models were criticized for their shortcomings.

Finally, the American Psychological Association’s modern definition of anxiety disorders demonstrates how contemporary psychology seeks to establish clearer diagnostic boundaries to guide interventions. By clarifying conceptual gaps (such as ambiguities, misinterpretations, or overlaps between terms) and proposing their applications or solutions, the table provides readers with a deeper understanding of how psychological constructs evolve, how they are applied in clinical practice, and why precise terminology is essential for effective diagnosis and intervention.

Table 2

Clarification of psychological terms: organizational, clinical and forensic psychology

Author(s)	Year	Psychologic terms	Conceptual Gap or Confusion	Definition	Application or Proposed solution
Rachmad	(2022)	Management	The gap between classical management theory and human behavior at work	Organizational psychology studies management as the interaction between leadership, motivation, and	Applied in HR practices, leadership training, Organization development, and

					employee performance	workplace well-being.
Rag	(Trau	Confusio	Traum	Appli	
havan & Sandanapit chai	2024)	ma	n between acute stress and chronic trauma	Confusion between acute stress and chronic trauma	a refers to psychological and physiological responses following overwhelming events that exceed coping resources.	ed in clinical interventions such as trauma-focused CBT, EMDR, and resilience programs.
Hus	(Crimi	The gap	Forens	Appli	
s	2025)	nal	between legal definitions of crime and psychological assessment	The gap between legal definitions of crime and psychological assessment	ic psychology examines criminal behavior through psychological theories, personality traits, and environmental factors.	ed in criminal profiling, offender rehabilitation, and expert testimony in court.
Fur	(Beha	Misunder	A	Appli	
nham	2021)	vioral pattern	standings about whether is innate or learned	Misunderstandings about whether behavior is innate or learned	A behavioral pattern is a repeated and observable sequence of actions influenced by	ed in behavioral therapies, habit formation research, and organizationa

					reinforcement, l performance punishment, or analysis. modeling.	
ng	Kri	(Treat	Debate	Psycho	Appli
Johnson	& 2022)	ment		between biological cognitive behavioral approaches	logical treatment involves structured methods (psychotherapy , CBT, pharmacothera py integration) to reduce symptoms and improve functioning.	ed in clinical settings for mood disorders, anxiety, addiction, and personality disorders.

Note. Based on documentary analysis among organizations, *Clinical and Forensic Psychology (2021-2025)*.

The second table integrates five key psychological terms drawn from different subfields: organizational psychology, clinical psychology, forensic psychology, behavioral analysis, and therapeutic practice. By including concepts such as management, trauma, criminal behavior, patterns of behavior, and treatment, the table highlights the diversity of psychological research and its applications across individual and social contexts.

The comparative structure highlights how each term is linked to a specific author or theoretical tradition, while drawing attention to conceptual gaps that often lead to misunderstandings, as the distinction between stress and trauma or the tension between legal and psychological perspectives in forensic settings. In addition, the definitions provided place each concept within its theoretical framework, and the applications demonstrate its relevance for practice, from workplace interventions to psychotherapy, offender rehabilitation, and behavioral change.

In general, the table serves as a tool to clarify terminology and connect theory with practice, making complex constructs more accessible for both academic analysis and professional application.

Table 3

Clarification of psychological terms: emotional intelligence and environmental psychology

Author(s)	Year	Psychological terms	Conceptual Gap or Confusion	Definition	Application or Proposed solution
Pelaez, Dabija, & Ene	(2021)	Empathy	Confusion between empathy, sympathy, and compassion	The ability to understand and share another person's emotional experience without losing objectivity.	Applied in psychotherapy (client-centered therapy), conflict resolution, and healthcare communication.
Rachmad	(2022)	Emotional intelligence	The gap between IQ-based intelligence and affective-social competencies	Emotional intelligence involves recognizing, understanding, and managing one's own emotions and those of others.	Applied in leadership development, workplace performance, and educational programs.
Gas & Seiter,	(2022)	Social psychology	Confusion between individual	The scientific study of how	Applied in group therapy,

			behavior and group dynamics	thoughts, feelings, and behaviors are influenced by the presence of others.	marketing, and organizational change, and prejudice reduction.	
ey	Dav (2021)	(2) ent clinical	Treatm sion between biological vs. psychotherapeutic approaches	Confu sion between biological vs. psychotherapeutic approaches	Psycho logical treatment refers to structured methods (CBT, psychodynamic therapy, and integrative approaches) for reducing distress and improving functioning.	Appli ed in mental health care for depression, anxiety, and personality disorders.
ge, Byrka, Brugger, Henn, Sparks & Urban,	Lan (2023)	(2) mental	Environ gap between the physical environment and psychological well-being	The gap between the physical environment and psychological well-being	The study of how physical surroundings (urban, natural, and built environments) affect human behavior and mental health.	Appli ed in urban planning, stress reduction, workplace design, and sustainability practices.

Note. Based on documentary analysis of emotional intelligence, social, and environmental Psychology (2021-2025).

Table 3 brings together five psychological constructs that emphasize the interaction between the individual, the social environment and clinical practice. The inclusion of

empathy and emotional intelligence highlights the central role of affective and interpersonal processes in understanding human behavior. While empathy focuses on the ability to connect with another's emotional state, emotional intelligence extends this capacity by emphasizing regulation, self-awareness and relational abilities.

The incorporation of social psychology places these constructs in a broader context, showing how individual thoughts and behaviors are shaped by group dynamics and social influence. This serves as a bridge between the personal and collective dimensions of psychology. In contrast, treatment represents the practical and clinical application of psychological theory, showing how conceptual clarity translates into methods that reduce discomfort and improve functioning. Finally, environmental psychology broadens the scope by recognizing the impact of physical and ecological contexts on mental health, highlighting how the environment influences general human well-being.

Taken together, these constructs demonstrate the importance of linking intrapersonal skills, social interaction, clinical practice and environmental factors to provide a more holistic understanding of psychological functioning and its applications. in the glossary section there is a more comprehensive and diversified glossary with 300 words in English and Spanish terms.

Description By The Psychology Area

English psychological lexicon encompasses various topics, including disorders, cognitive processes, behaviors, and even more for the emergence of artificial intelligence. With the growth of new vocabulary, many terms lack exact translations or possess sophisticated meanings that require comprehension within their original context. Consequently, exact terminology with accurate translation and thorough contextual analysis is required for the correct interpretation and application of this technical vocabulary in psychological contexts.

The different disciplines of psychology are: Basic Psychology, Educational Psychology, Social Psychology, Cognitive Psychology, Organizational Psychology, Clinical Psychology, Forensic Psychology, Health Psychology, Neuroscientific Psychology or Neuropsychology, Environmental Psychology, Community Psychology, and Art Psychology.

Basic Psychology

Basic psychology is crucial for understanding the operations of the mind. It analyzes cognitive processes, encompassing memory, emotion, learning, and perception of the environment. These concepts may seem esoteric at first glance; however, they underlie all of our behaviors, from daily decision-making to understanding others. Myers and DeWall (2022) argue that basic psychology lays the foundation for various fields of applied psychology, providing key insights into human cognition and behavior.

Understanding psychological terminology is essential not only for academic success and report writing, but also for understanding oneself and others in relation to behavior and cognition. In our modern society, where mental health is an important topic of debate, understanding and using this terminology facilitates clearer and more responsive communication. Halen and Ink (2023) emphasize this point through the concept of “psychological literacy,” which they define as the application of psychological knowledge in a meaningful, ethical, and pragmatic way.

Understanding principles such as perception, memory, emotion, motivation, and reinforcement can improve decision-making and strengthen relationships, whether you are a student, teacher, parent, or professional. The American Psychological Association (2022) asserts that mastering psychological terminology facilitates personal growth and fosters interpersonal relationships. Consequently, psychological literacy serves as an essential tool for navigating daily life with increased awareness and sensitivity.

Educational Psychology

Educational psychology is a discipline that examines the processes by which individuals acquire and preserve knowledge within educational settings. It also examines cognitive, emotional, and social learning processes and their influence on pedagogy and education. The aim is to apply psychological principles to enhance teaching techniques and promote learner growth (Woolfolk, 2019). Nowadays, this field seeks to establish more efficient and supportive learning environments that address to varied student requirements.

Educational psychology is crucial in formal education and daily interactions. In educational settings, it helps teachers develop effective teaching strategies that are tailored to students' developmental stages, learning preferences, and individual needs. Understanding theories such as Piaget's stages of cognitive development and Vygotsky's sociocultural theory

enables educators to create appropriate learning experiences (Slavin, 2020). This knowledge can contribute to creating favorable classroom dynamics that promote motivation and participation.

Outside the classroom, educational psychology cultivates lifelong learning skills such as motivation, self-regulation, and problem solving, which are important for personal and professional development. It addresses issues such as learning difficulties, behavioral problems, and classroom management, thereby creating an inclusive and supportive environment based on psychological principles (Ormrod, 2020). It also helps individuals adapt effectively to various life challenges and learning environments.

Social psychology

Social psychology investigates the impact of others on individuals' thoughts, feelings, and behaviors. Authors investigate the processes that facilitate the development of relationships and connect individuals, including conformity, leadership, persuasion, and prejudice, through empirical research. Research conducted by Hogg and Vaughan (2023) underscores the essential function of social psychology and its influence on attitude formation across various groups with distinct social and economic attributes.

Both in the academic and in the work environment, group psychology is applied in various fields such as psychology, education, social work, business and public health (Smith and Mackie, 2024). Its principles form the basis of programmes aimed at changing risk behavior, raising awareness of social issues and developing effective leadership. They also highlight the ability of groups to foster collaboration and empower individuals to achieve successful goals. All this is possible when you have open-minded individuals who are receptive to both observation and praise, for the sake of the necessary progress.

In this perspective, it is clear that motivating interactions transcend intimate engagements. Motivation may stem from affiliations with larger groups and organizations, as individuals pursue belonging, status, or opportunity to impact unfamiliar individuals (Grant & Shandell, 2022). These social connections underscore the profound interconnection between our objectives and endeavors and the social contexts we traverse.

At the same time, relationships can serve as a source of demotivation. It is worth considering how many more peaks of performance might have been achieved were it not for

the deflating impact of certain social interactions. Indeed, work motivation involves the psychological forces that direct, energize, and sustain effort in jobs, projects, and tasks, forces that are continually shaped, for better or worse, by our social connections.

Group thinking demonstrates how excessive adherence to consensus can lead to inconsistent or inappropriate group decisions. In this sense, social psychology focuses on the study of this phenomenon to understand and mitigate its effects through the analysis of behavior, attitudes, and group thinking processes (Shaukat, 2024). Similarly, social pressure has a significant impact on adolescents, generating behaviors that encourage risk-taking and cooperative action, according to context and thinking (Cialdini & Goldstein, 2024)

Psychological goals are important in determining how people internalize and respond to social expectations. In addition, the development of empathy (the emotional ability to understand and connect with others' feelings) has been shown to be a protective factor in interpersonal relationships for mediating complex situations. In conclusion, empathy is a common trait that fosters strong interpersonal relationships and creates opportunities to reduce conflict (Yin & Wang, 2023).

Cognitive Psychology

Currently, it is essential to analyze how cognitive processes are affected in people subjected to high levels of stress. Work overload, tension, and worry can diminish or even block individuals' cognitive abilities. Flood and Keegan (2022) illustrate this in their research on military personnel, a group that frequently performs complex cognitive operations under conditions of intense stress. The need to perform various physical and mental tasks under pressure, often with great responsibility, has given rise to the term “tactical athlete” to describe these professionals. The impact of this stress can cause significant deterioration in cognitive performance, with important consequences for the success of military operations and the well-being of personnel, especially in combat scenarios.

Understanding the nature of stress and the resilience of cognitive functioning under these conditions is crucial. This knowledge allows us to improve the subjective experience of stress and assess how it affects performance in complex cognitive tasks, contributing to the design of strategies that enhance coping skills and efficiency in high-pressure situations (Flood & Keegan, 2022).

Cognitive theories often use an information-processing framework to explain how our internal states and the outside world are represented in the mind. Such representations are powerful tools: they can make certain latent traits visible while hiding others, thereby affecting behaviors that rely on the emphasized aspects (Peelen & Downing, 2023).

So, it's really important to study cognitive processes because they affect how we see, understand, and respond in communication situations. A deep understanding of cognitive ideas is very important, especially in psychology. Psychologists can do better evaluations, write reports that are backed up by facts, and offer diagnoses that are based on a deep understanding of the mental processes that affect how people act when they fully understand these notions.

Cognitive psychology is very important in real life, such as in clinical practice, education, and organizational consulting. Experts can come up with ways to help people with mental health problems, create tailored teaching methods, and make the workplace more productive by understanding how the mind works. Research on episodic memory and collaborative dynamics has led to the creation of strategies that make group learning better and reduce memory biases (Nie et al., 2025).

Thus, practitioners gain from evidence-based instruments that enhance decision-making, promote learning, and bolster overall cognitive health. By utilizing ideas from cognitive psychology, professionals can cultivate workplaces that enhance mental agility, mitigate cognitive overload, and facilitate adaptive thinking. The extensive applicability underscores the essential importance of cognitive psychology in multiple practical fields.

Simultaneously, At the same time, it is important to examine the definition of intelligence offered by psychologists, as this concept provides a comprehensive understanding of cognitive processes and highlights the development of cognitive psychology. Intelligence is usually composed of various skills and abilities that reflect the cognitive capabilities of an individual, and professionals should be trained to scientifically assess the role of cognitive psychology (Cherry, 2022).

Understanding these complexities allows psychologists and related professionals to better assess individual differences and develop relevant solutions tailored to each case according to their findings. Therefore, accurate and effective care fosters the development of healthy communities and stable environments.

Organizational Psychology

Koutroubas and Galanakis (2022) emphasize the fundamental significance of Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory in influencing organizational behavior and management practices, referencing Gibson (2004), who highlighted its extensive effect on Human Resources Development (HRD). This structure helps with programs to increase performance, make cross-cultural training easier, and encourage self-regulation. It also lets firms tailor learning programs to match the individual needs of their employees. As a result, this helps employees grow and makes the company more effective.

On the other hand, Koutroubas and Galanakis (2022) show that optimism makes the combination of learning and work environment more beneficial. This concept is crucial in contexts such as skills upgrading, performance appraisals, goal setting, incentive structures, career development, and strategic decision-making. All these areas align closely with organizational psychology, which examines how individual traits and cognitive patterns shape workplace behavior. Also, recognizing these psychological factors helps foster environments where all company members, including owners, managers, employees, and supervisors, can reach their full potential in a culture that is supportive and productive, too.

This approach highlights the importance of linking aspects such as personality, self-control, self-efficacy, and autonomy with job performance. According to Christiansen and Tett (2013), Johnson and Hezlett demonstrate a significant relationship between people's perception of control over their activities and their understanding of task complexity, which includes self-efficacy and autonomy. These factors are essential for achieving good performance. Thus, these connections underscore the importance of organizational psychologists considering the individual as a whole when fostering their personal, social, and professional development.

Some theories in the field of organizational psychology maintain that this discipline is closely related to topics such as leadership, team cohesion, organizational culture, and burnout syndrome, among others. Therefore, several topics are linked to other branches of psychology, such as basic, social, and cognitive psychology, highlighting the interdisciplinary nature of understanding behavior and performance in the workplace. This comprehensive view allows organizations to more effectively address complex human interactions in order to strengthen healthier and more productive workplaces.

Clinical Psychology

Clinical psychology is a branch of psychology focused on the assessment, diagnosis, and treatment of mental, emotional, and behavioral disorders. Combines scientific principles, theoretical frameworks and clinical experience to understand complex human problems and promote mental health (American Psychological Association, 2020). Clinical psychologists use various methods such as psychological assessments, interviews, and observations to develop customized treatment programs in order to seek emotional and mental stability in diagnosed patients.

Additionally, they frequently work with patients suffering from disorders such as depression, anxiety, trauma-related disorders, and severe psychopathology. Practitioners prioritize evidence-based interventions by promoting recovery and personal growth, ensuring that therapeutic approaches are based on the latest research and best practices (Kazdin, 2017).

Clinical psychology is important not only for the treatment of mental disorders but also to improve the quality of life by helping people develop resilience and face life challenges. Therefore, clinical psychologists are also valuable members of interdisciplinary care teams (such as educational institutions, foundations, polyclinics, social assistance centers, etc.) because they provide psychological expertise that enhances comprehensive patient care (Norcross & Wampold, 2019).

The terminology related to clinical psychology is extensive and encompasses diverse behaviors, theories, and experiences grounded in basic and cognitive psychology. These are two central areas that offer a precise framework for analysis and understanding based on a given theory. Clinical psychology is particularly relevant, as it is essential for reducing the effects of mental illness and promoting overall well-being (physical, mental, and emotional) in individuals.

Forensic Psychology

Forensic psychology is the science that exclusively studies psychological principles and methods to address issues in criminal and civil legal proceedings. This branch encompasses diverse activities, such as assessing competency to stand trial, evaluating the mental state of the accuser, and conducting risk assessments (Neal & Line, 2022). Furthermore, forensic psychologists are able to analyze behavioral patterns to better understand criminal motivations and future risks. These assessments assist courts in making

decisions based on a forensic specialist's report regarding sentencing, treatment, and supervision.

Beyond clinical assessments, forensic psychologists also advise on issues such as the reliability of eyewitness testimony, jury selection, and interrogation practices, thus guiding legal actors in making evidence-based decisions (Goldfarb et al., 2023). By integrating other areas of psychology, such as clinical, social, and cognitive psychology, forensic psychologists help the judicial system understand the behavior of prosecutors in purely legal contexts. Ultimately, this overview allows for a more accurate assessment of the accused and witnesses.

In addition, since approximately 20% of erroneous forensic evidence is involved in erroneous convictions based on exculpatory evidence, the involvement of psychologists is necessary to correctly interpret such evidence and inform the jury about its limitations (Goldfarb et al., 2023). Forensic psychologists, whether consultants or experts, assist defense and prosecution teams by providing an objective and scientifically sound assessment of the accused's cognitive state and its likely behavioral consequences.

Similarly, a study by Sharda and Wright (2023) found that forensic psychiatry is rarely included in medical school curricula; however, it is a complex and important lesson students need to know today. The study also highlights the important contribution of this field to medical and related students as a fundamental part of the basic curriculum in psychiatry and psychology. These contributions include general skills and knowledge, such as ethical decision-making and emotional management.

In addition, forensic psychologists' expert testimony can help interpret the accused's mental capacity, influence decisions, and guide parole boards. This crucial role underlines the importance of his experience in the judicial system. Knowledge of forensic mental health also paves the way for important innovations in education, teaching, and research, especially at the undergraduate level.

Health Psychology

Health psychology is the empirical examination of the impact of psychological, behavioral, and social factors on health, disease, and medical care. Combining these components of psychology and medicine gives rise to new insights into how stress, emotions, beliefs, and coping strategies influence physical well-being (Taylor & Stanton, 2023). Health

psychology, from a biopsychosocial perspective, affirms that health encompasses not only the absence of disease but also a holistic approach to physical, mental, and social well-being (Garzón & Caro, 2014).

Instead, it examines how people manage chronic diseases, follow medical recommendations and maintain healthy lifestyles. Taylor and Stanton's book (2023) on "The Psychology of Health," demonstrates how psychological, behavioral, and social factors influence health outcomes. It also examines areas such as stress, adherence, prevention and social support, demonstrating through research and case studies how psychological principles guide healthy behaviors.

Therefore, health psychology is essential since it impacts various domains of psychology, including clinical, social, and occupational psychology, by emphasizing preventive, behavioral change, and patient-centered care (Garzón & Caro, 2014). Its impact is evident in how psychological interventions assist individuals in managing stress, enhancing resilience, improving sleep, and better regulating illnesses such as diabetes and hypertension. Health psychologists often create and implement initiatives that promote healthy living, with the goal of reducing risk factors and improving people's quality of life (Taylor & Stanton, 2023).

Neuroscientific Psychology

Neuroscientific psychology is an important discipline within the broader field of psychology, which examines the connections between brain anatomy, neural mechanisms, and human behavior. This discipline aims to elucidate how brain networks support cognitive functions, emotions, and decision-making by merging methodologies from neuroscience and psychology (Pradeep et al., 2024).

Their research area is related to neuroeducation, an interdisciplinary field that integrates neuroscience into education to improve strategies and outcomes with meaningful learning. In addition, Pradeep and colleagues (2024) claim that these findings are important for basic and cognitive psychology as they help us understand how emotions work and how they can be influenced by learning mechanisms.

Another neuroscientific study, entitled "Neuroscience and Mental Health: Connecting Biology and Behavior," reveals the fundamental link between neuroscience and mental health, showing how brain biology affects behavior and emotional states (Reddy, 2024). the

author emphasizes the bidirectional nature of this relationship, where exposure to environmental factors and treatments such as psychotherapy can have a significant impact on people's ability to cope with simple and complex situations.

This perspective demonstrates the robust relationship among neuroscience, cognitive psychology, and clinical psychology due to the multidisciplinary approach that addresses mental health disorders through new methods for giving a diagnosis and early intervention based on neuroscience. On the other hand, Privitera, Ng, and Chen (2025) found that while aging often decreases cognitive and brain functions associated with learning, crystallized skills and implicit learning are often unaffected.

Environmental Psychology

Environmental psychology is a fundamental aspect to consider in the design and construction of recreational areas, especially when they are planned for therapeutic purposes. These spaces provide community members with fresh, safe, and relaxing environments that promote recovery from illness, overcoming depression, or engaging in physical activity, whether in neighborhoods, communities, or even cities. According to Devlin (2018), it is now essential that professions related to design and planning prioritize the creation of recreational spaces in order to strengthen people's emotional, environmental, and physical health.

In his work, the author summarizes research on the physical environment of educational spaces for children aged 3 to 18, highlighting that environmental factors directly affect well-being, satisfaction, effectiveness, and health in both homes and workplaces. He also highlights the positive influence of natural or naturalistic recreational environments on mental and physical health, cognition, and social relationships, complemented by an analysis of human detention and its link to the physical environment, as it contributes to the emotional and physical well-being of individuals (Devlin,2018).

The book highlights the value of therapeutic spaces for the general well-being of people (children, young people, and adults), using gardens as an example: designs for patients, specific areas for staff, and urban green spaces with significant potential for promoting holistic health (emotional and physical).

Community Psychology

The book “Introduction to Community Psychology: Becoming an Agent of Change” offers a comprehensive look at community psychology through a social justice lens. The authors highlight how many societal problems, such as poverty, homelessness, unemployment, crime, racism, and unequal resource distribution, are most effectively addressed by prevention and systemic change.

They say that only looking at individual symptoms misses the bigger structural problems in the community. The goal is to find solutions that will last, and community psychologists, as experts, work closely with community members to combine study with action. This method makes sure that all interventions are fair to all cultures, which has a real effect on a community (Jason, Glantsman, O'Brien, & Ramian, 2019).

This book is especially important for understanding the role of community psychology, as it provides intellectual precision and pragmatic methodologies for community settings. Furthermore, its open-access format broadens awareness of the field's commitment to social justice, making it a significant example of accessibility and equity in global education. Furthermore, by reaching diverse audiences around the world, it helps ensure that critical discussions about community well-being are not limited to privileged spaces.

Art Psychology

The use of the arts as a therapeutic modality is deeply rooted in human history. From primitive rock art to ceremonial healing tools, artistic expression has served to express feelings, spread and enrich human experiences throughout history. The World Health Organization published a comprehensive report that highlights the importance of evidence supporting the impact of art on individual health and well-being (Karkou et al., 2022).

To address this issue, Karkou et al. (2022) review extensive research by an international group of experts in art psychology and creative arts therapy. Their research is based on exploring diverse creative forms, encompassing visual arts, music, dance, and theater, along with specialized techniques such as music therapy, art therapy, drama therapy, dance-movement therapy, and integrated methodologies. This allows for the pursuit of mental well-being in people with mental health disorders.

Moreover, recent studies have highlighted the physiological benefits of artistic practice. That's why authors Bower et al. (2021) and Hunt et al. (2021) demonstrate the

positive effects music has on cognitive function. Thus, art therapy has been shown to improve the quality of sleep in young people (according to an object of study). Similarly, Sawazi et al. (2020) demonstrated that the practice of visual arts and art therapy brings neurological and physical benefits to people with Alzheimer's disease, highlighting the important contribution of the arts to general health (mental, physical, emotional, etc.).

DISCUSSION

More and more often, the use of English has been rapidly increasing around the world in different areas, such as medicine, business, law, science, and others. English for academic purposes, as a subfield of English for specific purposes, has emerged to empower and equip learners to master English language skills and assertive communication skills needed for specific areas of knowledge or professional fields. These branches of English have potentially influenced the English language learning process in a significant way.

As stated by Halliday (2004), the relevance of these approaches has originated from the difficulty that learners have experienced and struggled when trying to share their thoughts using academic and professional language. For that reason, these areas of English incorporate into their processes the acquisition of terms learners will have to master to be able to make comparisons between choices in words, justify their use, knowing the forms and inflection of the words, applying in context vocabulary and forms of expression in specific academic disciplines (Goldenberg, 2008, p. 2). Thus, in this section, an analysis and reflections upon the implications of constructing a specialized and technical glossary in the psychology area are done. The focus is on contributing not just in the academic field, but also providing a social and professional impact through the integration of psychological terminology into the creation of this glossary.

First, the development of this product has revealed the relevance and complex nature of psychological language. As a broad and extensive discipline, Psychology includes a wide range of methodologies, theoretical frameworks, and concepts. This variety reveals the multifaceted nature and richness of the field. Therefore, it was essential to revise a large amount of literature to systematize terminology and offer definitions in such a way as to strengthen the understanding of this discipline from an academic, clinical, and everyday context perspective.

In addition, the application of the English for Academic Purposes (ESP) approach has been a potential pedagogical key to developing a deep understanding of human behavior, mental processes, and emotional functioning without barriers of language, time, and place. By acquiring and increasing the size of the vocabulary depth and size toward psychology, learners can be assisted to master their competencies in professional-related, social, and other aspects required in the academic context. In the same way, the terminology and selected vocabulary for this purpose have a significant implication in the process of learning based on this approach.

This branch of English has also facilitated learners to have better access to international resources, such as relevant literature from international authors, participate in global academic events, and share new findings in global contexts. Similar to what Scarcella (2003) and Sekhar (2020) have indicated, there are three dimensions that academic language proficiency needs to cover: linguistic, cognitive, and socio-cultural psychological. Therefore, this study agrees with that statement since it has been demonstrated that English for Academic Purposes not just expands linguistic skills, but also boosts cognitive processes of association, application in context, classification, critical thinking, ethical awareness, reasoning, and more (Moncayo-Ortiz, 2023).

This is in concordance with what Syaufika and Ambarwati (2023) stated about the relevance of the English for Academic Purposes approach. In today's globalized world, effective and assertive communication skills in English are quite important to succeed and grow professionally, particularly in the psychology field. Psychologists and therapists around the world are aiming to gain more and more followers through social media, which is an indicator of or a path to success. In the same line, English for academic purposes has become a relevant factor in university curriculum since it focuses on preparing learners to communicate assertively using terms that are related to their field of study to show their expertise in the field.

Similar results were produced by Maierova (2024) in research in which Instagram was implemented as a potential tool that has facilitated the process of the English for academic purposes (ESAP) approach. It is due to the fact that the reduction in the connection and technology gaps has led to a transformation of how psychologists are interacting with patients. It coincides with the study of Diel et al. (2024), who stated that nowadays digital interventions are

a way to help people with mental disorders, using technological tools such as platforms or means as social media to transmit knowledge, awareness, or even for digital monitoring.

This academic foundation in psychology is crucial for promoting a responsible interpretation of psychological phenomena and helps explain complex issues related to the field. Also, it is crucial for informing clinical practices, influencing public policy, producing reliable data, and, no less importantly, contributing to society's well-being. Moreover, this term's acquisition process, as part of the academic involvement, fosters some competences required across multiple disciplines, professions, and areas of life, such as analyzing data, questioning assumptions, and presenting findings in an accurate and professional way of communication.

Third, another crucial element of this research is the interdisciplinary nature of the glossary. The reviewed literature is vast since it has explored many psychology subfields, such as clinical psychology, forensic psychology, organizational behavior, educational psychology, environmental psychology (Bello et al., 2025; Grant, 2024; Hawke et al., 2022; Villalpando-Flores, 2022; Bhavsar et al., 2018; Hoare et al., 2015; Amar & Torado, 2010), as well as the current role of artificial intelligence in this field and its effects (Diel et al., 2024; Guo et al., 2024).

Studying these authors' perspectives and results is essential for gaining a deep understanding of human behavior in various contexts. Moreover, comprehending the role of artificial intelligence in psychological practice represents a transformative era that is being reshaping how people understand, access, and support mental processes. Including terms that are related to AI and digital interventions in the glossary reflects how innovations and new trends are occurring in the profession, and anticipates a paradigm shift in how mental health is being approached. Thus, this highlights the need for a comprehensive glossary that resonates with the interdisciplinary nature of psychological science.

In addition, another crucial key of the glossary presented is the social inclusion approach. How it was mentioned previously, mental health has gained relevancy globally (Misra et al., 2019). This is a topic of concern for many, thanks to the work of several researchers who have promoted awareness campaigns aimed at reducing stigma and encouraging help-seeking behavior to address or prevent issues related to mental health. such

as the one from Tam et al. (2024), who focused on raising awareness on the importance of comprehending people's emotional well-being and human behavior.

For that reason, by offering clear and accessible language, it promotes not only professionals in the area, but also families, or people in general who are interested in learning more about human behavior to understand psychological issues. Hence, it leads to the improvement of the quality of support and care, and encourages people to search for help when they need it. Also, it contributes to generating ethical responsibility, offering a reliable resource for those who are not experts in this field of study.

Similarly, this product has a potential role as a learning tool. Educators can incorporate this glossary into their didactic resources in such a way that learners can use it to review concepts, connecting theory with practice, and gain a deeper understanding of complex terms.

Also, professionals can use it to be implemented in medical software that provides guidance to generate diagnoses for specific issues, relying on it for its accurate transmission of information into practice. The academic rigor and the solid epistemological characteristics of the glossary guarantee that the definitions are not colloquial, broad, or trivial; on the contrary, they offer an accurate interpretation or use of the terms since they are based on scientific and well-supported research sources.

Moreover, it is also worth highlighting the glossary's potential for research. This product is a valuable artifact for composing academic texts, such as essays, reports, scientific articles, chapters of books, and thesis writing. This standardized compilation of technical terms facilitates the writing process on research, offering guidance in consistency, meaningfulness, and accuracy of the information.

Another relevant point to reflect on is that this glossary is aligned with the current social phenomena. Since the COVID-19 pandemic, people's mental health around the world was deeply impacted. This global event turns out to be a powerful trigger, bringing to life a vast number of cases of anxiety and depression. It was as if the pandemic acted as a catalyst, exposing and magnifying the emotional burdens that humans were already carrying.

When masks came off, so did the emotional barriers. It was too overwhelming for people to deal with this painful experience, so being open to the world became necessary, as individuals could no longer hide what they had been carrying inside for years. In other words,

the need to relieve their emotional and mental struggles became unavoidable. That moment marked a turning point when people began to dissolve the stigma about mental health. As something that was becoming a topic of new concern, people realized that the fear or shame of being judged no longer had power.

The disapproval or discrimination that people faced when experiencing mental health conditions became obsolete. Therefore, the necessity for people to understand their emotions started to rise, even if their majors or careers are not related to this field of study. It proves the relevance of the field of Psychology, not just for professionals and academics, but also for common people with a high interest in understanding more about how human beings' mental and emotional work, and more about the patterns of behavior.

In the same line, another area of concern that is connected with the growing interest in comprehending deeply the human behavior is the exponential rise in criminal activities and problematic behaviors observed in not just big countries, but also small ones. This phenomenon has been detected with more frequency in small nations that are especially located in Latin America. This area has been the target of organized crime, including narco-trafficking, extortion, human trafficking, kidnapping, vacunas (extortion fees), child trafficking, and more, which has led to a profound impact in social and psychological terms.

In such atmospheres, the demand for professionals who are able to analyze criminal behavior from a psychological perspective has increased. Forensic psychology is the new focus for many who want not just to assist in investigations, but also in creating some criminal profiling, and developing some strategies for prevention and detection of those who are affected by violence in disadvantaged communities from underprivileged areas. Professionals such as police officers and forensic psychologists seek psychological knowledge to prevent future crimes and improve the level of success in criminal investigations.

Therefore, the glossary aims at presenting terms that are not just addressed in general psychology. It also includes terminology that is related to more specialized and complex subfields and branches of this field. The authors have considered it relevant to incorporate criminal and forensic psychological terms to strengthen the glossary and guarantee it serves as a valuable resource that reflects the real-world needs faced by developed and developing

nations alike, as well as exhibiting the diverse and evolving nature of psychological practices in different contexts and environments.

In addition, this chapter also aims to contribute to the research field of criminal and forensic psychology, as a basis or foundation resource for those who are emerging in these areas. Studies as those of Amar and Torado (2010) have demonstrated the importance of observing criminalistic phenomena and addressing actions that are concerning the legislative context. By providing clear and accessible terminology, it serves in the initial stages of academic and professional training in this area. Furthermore, it is intended to support future research related to profiling, the criminal mind, and a psychological understanding in criminal settings. This study seeks to assist learners, professionals, and researchers who are required to explore the complex dynamics of this field and to address challenges at the moment of communicating in academic, professional, and real-world contexts.

Not less importantly, it is confirmed that this glossary responds to one of the real-world concerns, “Mental Health”, and that it has shown a solid connection with areas of main concern as a way to address global crises and collective mental health issues, in terms of globalization and digitalization. Topics such as the cyberbullying, online comparison, and digital addiction are part of new psychological concerns, since they are reshaping the way how psychology is perceived now, it means that the form how humans interact, form relationships, emotional management, and communication are evolving with the fast growing of technology, AI, and connectivity.

In addition, the growing demand for mental health attention after the impact of pandemics, climate change, and political instability has created a necessity to be adaptive, ethical, transformative, and culturally informed without losing the human touch. Consequently, it was imperative to consider these shifts in the terms that the glossary includes as well. Hence, it proves that this product not only covers an interdisciplinary approach, but also extensive life areas.

In contrast to the review’s theories, it has been evident that poor literature on the pedagogical systematization of vocabulary was found, although a vast number of studies exist in the mental health field. It is imperative to state that this work adds value to the field of study since it is not just limited to a list of terms and their definitions, but also includes Spanish equivalents and updates bibliographic references. Carrying out pedagogical

systematization and vocabulary studies is crucial in the field of psychology, since 1. ensures coherence and conceptual clarity, 2. promotes interlinguistic and cultural understanding, 3. supports research and knowledge transfer, and 4. facilitates effective teaching and learning.

Firstly, psychology covers abstract and complex terms and concepts that can lead to misunderstandings or incorrect uses; as a result, research findings may be misinterpreted or misperceived. By classifying and organizing the terms accurately, ambiguity can be avoided, and psychology learners can communicate their thoughts and ideas in a more precise way. To illustrate, a misunderstanding in terminology that can impact diagnosis in psychology would be confusing a panic attack with an anxiety attack. If those terms are not clear, consider a treatment plan focused on long-term management of stress and cognitive reorganization, which can be applied instead of applying interoceptive exposure or panic-focused CBT. In other words, a simple terminology misunderstanding may lead to ineffective treatment, misdiagnosis, patient frustration, or even worsening of individuals' mental health.

Second, adding the Spanish translation in the glossary is relevant since psychology is a global field; therefore, students who are native and do not need to access and learn the same concepts and terms. In addition, in many cases, translations of psychological concepts are not made neatly, which can lead to misinformation and miscommunication in bilingual or multicultural contexts, especially in academic, professional, and research contexts. Proper translation guarantees that the nuance and meaning of the psychological terms are accurate.

Third, in terms of research, replicability and comparability are aspects that ensure the quality of a study. Therefore, consistent definitions in applied settings are crucial to document findings and outcomes accurately. In other words, researchers and practitioners in this field should use the same language to spread knowledge in a reliable and valid way. In addition, to replicate a study, researchers are required to measure variables the same way; in this line, accurate vocabulary leads to consistent operational definitions, and it ensures that measurements and methods are connected across studies.

Fourth, a pedagogical systematization of terms enables a well-structured way to teach concepts in the field of psychology, which is essential for students who are unfamiliar with academic or scientific language. Also, it provides clarity and consistency in a field of study that leads with complex terminology, enabling students to understand the relationships and

connections between concepts and terms and reducing confusion in overlapping or similar terminology.

To sum up, this discussion area reveals that the chapter has presented not just a pedagogical, but also a transformative and innovative approach. It is pedagogical because terminology has been chosen, classified, and organized with assertiveness as a way to facilitate the learning process of acquiring and increasing new vocabulary in English for specific and academic purposes. However, it is also innovative since it evidences an ethical commitment and socially responsible practices, in a world where language and communication can either strengthen or destroy societies.

Therefore, this glossary should not be used or perceived as a final and finished product, but also as an innovative and transformative source, open to updates, changes, improvements, and expansion. As the world is evolving across time, so too do new concerns arise about patterns of human behavior. New emergency and abrupt social dynamics and psychological phenomena are constantly surfacing, requiring careful and close attention to be observed, explored, and studied. This transformation in progress has highlighted the relevance of remaining responsive and ready to address the complexity of human experience.

CONCLUSIONES

Psychological knowledge is gaining increasing importance in social, academic, and professional settings. This article is aimed at supporting the need of bridging the gap between complex academic psychological terminology and real-world understanding through the systematization of a glossary in Psychology. The design and development of a pedagogically well-structured systematization of vocabulary not only contributes to the linguistic field, but also reflects a social responsibility action. The study reveals the importance of this pedagogical approach as a tool for promoting conceptual clarity, enhancing multidisciplinary and cross-cultural communication, facilitating the replicability in research, and supporting the teaching and learning process.

By collecting relevant psychology terms in English, with their Spanish translation and definitions, this chapter provides a reliable resource that presents both academic rigor and practical applicability. In addition, it is a solid support for learners at all levels since this glossary plays a vital role in applying English for academic purposes (ESP), preparing and

empowering students with tools that facilitate the accurate use of academic literature in communication in specialized settings, and participating in international psychological research.

In addition, this glossary includes terminology that is aligned across multiple subfields and branches of Psychology, such as forensic, educational, organizational, clinical, and environmental. This evidences the glossary's interdisciplinary extent and its importance in real-world concerns. This breadth in the scope emphasizes that psychology is not limited to theoretical and conceptual knowledge, but it also stands out for its practicality as a science that is evolving in time, and should be communicated in a proper and accurate way to serve diverse individuals in an ethical and responsible way.

Finally, the design of the glossary is intended to evolve with the field, adapting emerging psychological phenomena to support a deeper understanding of human behavior and mental health processes, in accordance with technological advancement, globalization, and social change. Therefore, this chapter contributes meaningfully not just to the academic and professional contexts but also to the ethical advancement of psychology by strengthening language as a medium for communication, learning, research, and the mental care system.

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